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Experimental investigation of the isothermal flow field in an air staged multiswirl 100% hydrogen burner

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Abstract. Hydrogen is a promising fuel for decarbonizing energy production and aeronautical propulsion. Even though hydrogen is a zero-carbon fuel, its unique physical and chemical properties pose significant challenges for use in conventional combustion systems, particularly due to potential issues with combustion stability and increased NO_x emissions. This study investigates a 100% H₂ double coaxial swirl burner, adapted from a prior CH₄/H₂ burner design. The burner features two concentric, co-rotating swirling jets, with a fast H₂ premixing stage positioned just before the nozzle outlet to mitigate flashback risks. We present a preliminary analysis of the isothermal flow generated by two injector geometries, using Stereo PIV to capture detailed flow dynamics. In addition to examining the time-averaged flow field, we apply Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) to identify coherent structures within the flow. Results show that the two geometries produce distinct flow field configurations and varying intensities of reverse flow in the near-injection region (within 1–2 diameters downstream). Although similar patterns emerge further downstream, subtle differences in flow structure remain.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen is increasingly recognized as a key energy carrier in the transition toward low-carbon energy systems, owing to its potential for carbon-free combustion. Unlike hydrocarbon fuels, hydrogen combustion does not produce CO₂, making it an attractive option for reducing greenhouse gas emissions in power generation and propulsion systems. However, the direct use of hydrogen as a fuel poses significant challenges, including a high tendency for flashback, low ignition energy, high flame speeds, and susceptibility to thermoacoustic instabilities [1,2]. These issues necessitate the development of advanced burner designs capable of operating with 100% hydrogen while ensuring flame stability, safety, and low pollutant emissions.

Swirling flows are critical in a wide range of engineering applications, including gas turbines, liquid rocket engine injectors, industrial burners, and cyclone separators, due to their ability to enhance mixing and improve combustion efficiency [3,4]. The complexity and richness of swirling flows have driven extensive theoretical, experimental, and computational studies aimed at understanding their structure and behavior in various contexts [5,6].

In advanced combustion systems, particularly those used in gas turbines, double and multiple coaxial swirlers are commonly employed to enhance air–fuel mixing, thereby optimizing combustion [7]. The flow dynamics in coaxial swirl systems are more complex than those involving a single swirler, as the interaction between the coaxial swirling jets results in intricate flow patterns that influence combustion stability and emissions. Several studies have investigated how swirl levels and directions, such as

counter-rotating and co-rotating configurations, affect the flow field and combustion performance, providing valuable insights into how these configurations can influence flame stabilization and pollutant formation [8–11].

The burner analyzed in this work is specifically designed for the combustion of 100% hydrogen. It features a central premixed swirled injector that facilitates the mixing of hydrogen and air. The configuration is engineered to achieve rapid premixing, which is crucial for stable combustion with hydrogen. This is accomplished through the use of impinging jets, which enable effective mixing just before the reactants enter the combustion chamber. Such a design, combined with the use of rich hydrogen mixtures (with an equivalence ratio $\phi > 3$), minimizes the risk of flashback, an issue particularly critical due to hydrogen’s high diffusivity and flammability.

The co-rotating swirl system adopted in this burner is a slightly modified version of that developed and analyzed in previous research [12,13], where it was tested with CH_4/H_2 mixtures [14]. This burner configuration is expected to improve combustion stability and reduce emissions. Compared to those earlier studies, the present work experimentally investigates two configurations employing novel central injector geometries. However, the primary focus is on the characterization of the flow field under isothermal conditions, while investigations under reactive (combustion) conditions are currently underway. This study therefore provides a detailed comparison of the mean flow fields generated by the two injector designs. In addition, a phase-averaging technique based on Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) is implemented to investigate the presence of a precessing vortex core (PVC), a phenomenon known to significantly affect flow dynamics in swirling systems.

2. Designed burner geometry

The designed dual swirl burner in **Figure 1** is constituted of two main components: the burner base and the combustion chamber. The burner base consists of a cylindrical (converging) plenum, two coaxial tubes, a swirl generator and a flow rectifier.

Figure 1. a) Schematic representation of the designed burner and b) premixed injector.

The combustion chamber has an octagonal shape; four of the eight walls are made of stainless steel while the remaining four are transparent quartz for optical access. A hood is installed on top of the combustion chamber, promoting the discharge of the air and oil from the combustion chamber. The cylindrical plenum is used to inject the swirled secondary air around the gas gun. The stream is divided into axial \dot{V}_{ax} and tangential \dot{V}_{tan} air to impart a swirling motion to the secondary air stream. The axial air is injected at the bottom of the plenum and passes through the flow rectifier. The tangential air is injected through the swirl generator, characterized by 8 tangential holes. The secondary swirl degree can be controlled by varying the Split Ratio defined in Equation (1):

$$SR_s = \frac{\dot{V}_{tan}}{\dot{V}_{ax} + \dot{V}_{tan}} \quad (1)$$

representing the amount of tangential flowrate, \dot{V}_{tan} , over the sum of the axial, \dot{V}_{ax} , and tangential air flowrate. Eventually, the air flow is injected into the combustion chamber through an annular nozzle characterized by an external diameter of $D = 36mm$.

The two coaxial tubes are used to inject the premix air \dot{V}_{premix} and hydrogen \dot{V}_{H_2} . The premix air flows in the inner tube and is injected tangentially into the axial hydrogen stream (see **Figure 1**). The tangential injector is attached to the inner tube and can move along the axial direction inside the outer coaxial tube. The recess of the injector is fixed at 5 mm as shown in **Figure 1b**.

The injector consists of a cylindrical body and a crown at the lower part. The cylindrical body, characterized by a diameter D_{inj} , has three rows of 6 tangential holes of diameter $D_{tan} = 2mm$ that impart a swirling motion to the premix airflow. The crown, with a diameter $D_{crown} = 25mm$, contains 12 axial holes of diameter D_{ax} mm through which hydrogen flows. In this study two premixed injectors characterized by different geometries are tested: injectors A and B. In particular, the body diameter D_{inj} and the axial holes diameter D_{ax} are varied as reported in **Table 1**.

The geometrical swirl number of the secondary swirled jet is computed using Equation (2):

$$S_{g,s} = \frac{\pi R_{0,s} D}{2A_{T,s}} SR_s^2 \quad (2)$$

where $R_{0,s} = 38mm$ is the radial distance between the axis of each tangential channel from the swirler axis, $D = 36mm$ is the outlet diameter of the swirler, and $A_{T,s}$ is the total cross-sectional area of the tangential channels. The geometrical swirl number of the premixed injector is computed using Equation (3):

$$S_{g,p} = \frac{R_{0,p} D_{crown}}{18D_{tan}^2} SR_p^2 \quad (3)$$

where the radial distance between the axis of each tangential channel from the injector axis is $R_{0,p} = 0.5(D_{inj} - D_{tan} - 2t)$, in which t represents the thickness of the injector walls and SR_p is the split ratio of the premixed injector evaluated as described in Equation (4):

$$SR_p = \frac{\dot{V}_{premix}}{\dot{V}_{premix} + \dot{V}_{H_2,eq}} \quad (4)$$

where \dot{V}_{premix} is the premix air flowrate computed from the local equivalence ratio and $\dot{V}_{H_2,eq}$ is the air substituting hydrogen.

Table 1. List of geometrical and flow parameters of the two tested premixed injectors.

	Injector A	Injector B
Tangential holes number and diameter D_{tan}	18 x \emptyset 2 mm	18 x \emptyset 2 mm
Body diameter D_{inj}	16 mm	12 mm
Crown diameter D_{crown}	25 mm	25 mm
Axial holes number and diameter D_{ax}	12 x \emptyset 3 mm	12 x \emptyset 3.8 mm

3. Flow parameters

The burner is operated at an equivalent thermal power of $P_{th} = 12 \text{ kW}$, global equivalence ratio equal to $\phi_g = 0.45$, local equivalence ratio of $\phi_p = 3$ (i.e. $SR_p = 0.75$) and secondary split ratio $SR_s = 0.6$. To ensure safe burner operation, the hydrogen flowrate is substituted by an equivalent flowrate of air $\dot{V}_{H_2,eq} = 17.6 \text{ Nl/min}$ having the same momentum as hydrogen. The term equivalent thermal power refers to the thermal input that would result if hydrogen were used as fuel. The premix air flowrate is $\dot{V}_{premix} = 53.2 \text{ Nl/min}$ and the tangential and axial air flowrates in the secondary stream are $\dot{V}_{tan} = 181.0 \text{ Nl/min}$ and $\dot{V}_{ax} = 120.7 \text{ Nl/min}$ respectively.

The Reynolds number of the secondary air stream is evaluated multiplying the bulk velocity of the secondary jet $V_{bulk,s} = 15 \text{ m/s}$ by the hydraulic diameter of a circular crown and dividing by the air kinematic viscosity $\nu = 1.49 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ at ambient temperature. The Reynolds number of the premixed air jet is computed similarly but using the bulk velocity of the premixed jet $V_{bulk,p} = 2.6 \text{ m/s}$ and the diameter of the crown D_{crown} as characteristic dimension. The described parameters are summarized in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Flow parameters.

	Injector A	Injector B
Premixed jet geometrical swirl $S_{g,s}$		10
Premixed jet geometrical swirl $S_{g,p}$	2	1.2
Reynolds of the secondary jet Re_s		7013
Reynolds of the secondary jet Re_p		4279

4. Experimental setup

The experimental setup consists of the burner, the stereoscopic PIV and the air supply systems.

The S-PIV setup comprises two CMOS cameras with a sensor resolution of 5320 x 3032 pixels, operated in the 2 x 2 binning mode. Each camera is equipped with an interferential band pass filter (10 nm FWHM, centred at 532 nm) and mounted on a Scheimpflug adapter. Camera 1 is equipped with a 50mm focal length lens, while camera 2 has a 60mm lens; both lenses are set to an aperture of F#8. The two cameras observe the laser sheet from opposite sides, each positioned at approximately 45° with the particles' forward scattering direction, improving image illumination. The field of view in the horizontal direction is constrained to around 3.8D by the width of the quartz windows, while in the vertical direction, it is limited to approximately 2.9D by the camera sensor size.

A dual-cavity Nd:YAG laser emitting light at 532 nm is used to generate a light sheet of about 1.5 mm thickness. To visualize how the flow structures evolve along the axial direction, the laser sheet is aligned vertically and passes through the combustion chamber along the nozzle diameter.

Figure 2. Stereo-PIV experimental setup.

To reduce laser light reflections detected by the cameras, the inner surfaces of the metallic walls and the flange are coated with orange fluorescent paint (visible in **Figure 2**). The emission from this paint is effectively filtered out by the interferential filters, minimizing spurious reflections.

Both the annular and central jets are seeded with vaseline oil droplets ($\rho_{oil} = 880 \text{ kg/m}^3$ at 20°C) with a mean diameter of $d_p \cong 1-2 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, generated by two separate atomizers. The Stokes number $S_t = \tau_p/\tau_u$, which describes the ability of the tracer to follow the flow, is computed as the ratio between the characteristic response time of the oil droplets τ_p and the characteristic time scale of the flow field τ_u and must be much smaller than 1. The particle response time is computed with Equation (5):

$$\tau_p = \frac{\rho_{oil} d_p^2}{\mu_{air}} = 2.7 \text{ }\mu\text{s} \quad (5)$$

where μ_{air} is the dynamic viscosity of air. The characteristic time scale of the flow is estimated using Equation (6):

$$\tau_u = \frac{r_{W_{max}}}{W_{max}} = 1.6 \text{ ms} \quad (6)$$

where W_{max} is the maximum tangential velocity and $r_{W_{max}}$ is its corresponding radial position. This results in a Stokes number of $S_t = 0.0017$, confirming that the tracer fidelity condition is met.

5. Data acquisition and analysis

5.1. Stereo-PIV maps processing

Image acquisition and processing were carried out using Dantec's DynamicStudio 8.0. Stereo PIV is operated in double frame mode, and the time between pulses is set equal to $13 \text{ }\mu\text{s}$. For each injector, 1000 pairs of images were acquired by each camera at a frequency of 10 Hz. The background removal from the acquired PIV images is performed by subtracting the mean of 20 images captured without flow or seeding. The 3rd order polynomial method is used to dewarp the obtained images.

The PIV algorithm employs an iterative, multi-grid, and multi-pass approach based on cross-correlation. The final interrogation window size is set to 32 by 32 pixels with a 50% overlap. Vector validation was performed using both peak validation and universal outlier detection methods [15]. The resulting PIV maps have a spatial resolution of about $0.04D$. The out-of-plane velocity component was derived from the two in-plane velocity measurements. Misalignment errors between the laser sheet and the calibration target are corrected using the disparity vector map generated from the PIV images.

The relative statistical error of the mean velocity is given by $\varepsilon_{velocity} = 1.96/V_{bulk} \bar{v}'/\sqrt{N} = \pm 4\%$, where the bulk velocity, $V_{bulk} \cong 5.68$ m/s, is computed considering the total air flowrate and the external diameter D of the annular nozzle. The axial velocity standard deviation is $\bar{v}' \cong 4$ m/s. The sample size $N = 1000$ corresponds to statistically independent Stereo PIV measurements. This independence is ensured because the PIV sampling time, $t_{SPIV} = 1/10\text{Hz} \cong 0.1$ s, is much larger than twice the integral time scale $T_i = D/V_{bulk} \cong 0.006$ s.

5.2. Phase-average based on Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD)

To extract coherent flow structures and separate them from random fluctuations, a triple decomposition framework, introduced by Hussain and Reynolds [16], was employed. In this framework, the instantaneous velocity vector field is decomposed according to Equation (7):

$$\tilde{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \bar{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{x}) + \hat{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \mathbf{v}'(\mathbf{x}, t) \quad (7)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{x})$ represents the time-averaged velocity field, $\hat{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the coherent fluctuating velocity field and $\mathbf{v}'(\mathbf{x}, t)$ is the randomly fluctuating field. The phase-averaging aims to extract $\bar{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{x}) + \hat{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{x}, t)$ by sorting the instantaneous velocity maps according to the phase of oscillation $\theta(t)$ of the coherent fluctuation and averaging the maps within the same phase interval. The angle $\theta(t)$ can be obtained from an external reference signal [17] or extracted directly from time-resolved velocity maps [18].

In the present study, the Stereo PIV system operates at a frequency too low to temporally resolve coherent structures, and no external reference signal is available. Therefore, the phase angle is determined using the Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) [19]. POD decomposes the fluctuating velocity field into a linear combination of temporal coefficients $a_j(t)$ and spatial modes $\Psi_j(\mathbf{x})$ as expressed in Equation (8):

$$\hat{\mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{x}, t) + \mathbf{v}'(\mathbf{x}, t) = \sum_{j=1}^N a_j(t) \Psi_j(\mathbf{x}) \quad (8)$$

Originally introduced in fluid mechanics by Lumley [20] for extracting coherent structures in turbulent flows, POD has been extensively studied in numerous papers and books (see, for example, [21,22]). In this work, POD is implemented using the snapshot method proposed by Sirovich [23].

The phase angle $\theta(t)$ is then calculated using Equation (9), where $a_1(t)$ and $a_2(t)$ are the time coefficients of the two most energetic POD modes [19,24–26]:

$$\theta(j) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\lambda_1} a_1(t)}{\sqrt{2\lambda_2} a_2(t)} \right) \quad (9)$$

where λ_1 and λ_2 are the eigenvalues associated with the first and second POD, respectively. The velocity maps, reconstructed from the average map and the 1st and 2nd POD modes, are then sorted into phase bins of width $\Delta\theta$ according to their phase angles $\theta(j)$. Balancing angular resolution and statistical convergence, a phase bin width of $\Delta\theta = \pi/6$ radians (30°) is chosen, resulting in approximately 75 instantaneous reconstructed maps per bin and a total of 12 phase-averaged maps.

6. Results

6.1. Mean flow morphology

Figure 3 compares the time-average flow fields of the two injectors under study. More in detail, **Figure 3 a-b** represent the tangential velocity contour map together with the streamlines, while **Figure 3 c-d** show the axial velocity component together with the zero-velocity iso-lines which identify the reverse flow region. Both axial and radial coordinates are normalized with respect to the nozzle diameter D , while the velocity is normalized with respect to the bulk velocity V_{bulk} .

Even though the measured flow field structure for both injectors is almost similar, some differences due to the injector geometries can still be noticed. Vortex breakdown occurs for both injectors, and a corner recirculation vortex (CRV) is observed between the secondary swirled jet and the combustion chamber walls. The presence of this vortex is justified by the confinement in the chamber and entrainment in the swirled jet.

A central recirculation zone (CRZ) is observed along the burner axis. Because Injector A imparts a higher geometric swirl due to its larger head diameter, this zone is more intense for Injector A, and the minimum axial velocity occurs closer to the injector head compared to Injector B (**Figure 3 c-d**). In this configuration, the jet is wider and shifts the CRV downstream, as clearly shown in **Figure 3 a-b**. Owing to the larger passage area of Injector B, the axial velocity is weaker, especially at the nozzle outlet.

Figure 3. Time-averaged flow field. a) tangential velocity component and streamlines for Injector A and b) injector B. c) axial velocity component for Injector A and d) injector B. The axial coordinates corresponding to minimum axial velocity are syndicated by red line for Injector A and yellow line for Injector B.

6.2. Visualization of POD modes

Figure 4. a) Energy fraction as function of POD modes for Injector B. b) Phase diagram of the normalized time coefficients corresponding to the first two POD modes for Injector B.

The plot in **Figure 4a**, represents the energy fraction associated to each POD mode for Injector B. It is possible to notice that the energy fraction has a strongly decreasing trend, but the first two POD modes have a much higher energy level than all the others. Specifically, the combined energy of modes 1 and 2 accounts for 3 % of the total turbulent kinetic energy in Injector A and 5.1 % in Injector B. Although these values remain below the threshold suggested by Legrand et al. et al. [27], for unequivocal detection of coherent structures, the phase diagram constructed from the corresponding temporal coefficients (**Figure 4b**) still exhibits a roughly circular distribution, a signature of periodic flow behavior [24]. The

Figure 5. Contours of the first and second POD modes of the velocity components for Injector B: a) axial, b) e) tangential, and c) f) radial.

circle is, however, characterized by a scattered arrangement of the points, reflecting the relatively low energy contained in the first two modes.

Figure 5 displays the spatial structures of POD modes 1 and 2 for each velocity component. In every component, repetitive patterns appear, spatially phase-shifted with respect to one another. Such patterns are characteristic of coherent structures embedded in the swirling flow.

6.3. Phase-averaged velocity maps

This section presents the phase-averaged results for Injector B only, as Injector A exhibited qualitatively similar structures with some quantitative differences, which are not shown here for brevity.

Although the energy associated with the first two POD modes is relatively low, the phase-averaged velocity fields are sufficiently clear to permit physical interpretation. The phase-averaged axial velocity contours, normalized by the bulk velocity V_{bulk} , are shown in **Figure 6a-d** at four characteristic phases, corresponding to $\vartheta = 0^\circ$, 90° , 180° and 270° . These contour maps reveal clear asymmetries with respect to the burner axis.

Two main dynamical features can be identified. The first is the oscillation of the two jet structures associated with the exit of the secondary air stream. These structures, visible as yellow/orange regions of higher axial velocity are characterized by a periodic bending movement. The second dynamic feature is associated to the central recirculation region with blue color, which periodically shifts toward the left side at $\vartheta = 0^\circ$ and $\vartheta = 270^\circ$ and back to the right at $\vartheta = 90^\circ$ and $\vartheta = 180^\circ$ as shown in **Figure 6a-d**.

Figure 6. Normalized phase-averaged axial velocity component reconstructed from the first two POD modes.

These observations are consistent with the presence of a processing vortex core (PVC) in the flows under investigation.

7. Conclusions

This study presented an experimental investigation of the isothermal flow field generated by a 100% hydrogen, air-staged, dual-swirl burner. For safety reasons, air was used instead of hydrogen. Two premixed injector geometries were then tested and compared using stereoscopic Particle Image Velocimetry (S-PIV) measurements. Proper Orthogonal Decomposition (POD) was applied to the instantaneous velocity fields obtained from S-PIV in order to assess the presence of coherent structures, such as the Processing Vortex Core (PVC).

Despite the overall similarities in the flow structures, differences were observed between the two injectors due to their geometric characteristics. Injector A, with a higher geometrical swirl number, produced a more intense central recirculation zone (CRZ) compared to Injector B. Moreover, vortex breakdown occurred closer to the burner outlet for Injector A, influencing the extent and position of the recirculation regions.

POD analysis enabled the identification of coherent structures within the swirling flow, even though the energy associated with the leading modes was relatively low. Phase-averaged velocity fields revealed periodic lateral oscillations of the jet structures, indicating the presence of a processing vortex core (PVC), a key feature in strongly swirling flows.

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